

CONCEPT OF FAMILY: PRESENTATION AND REPRESENTATION OF FAMILY IN COMMERCIALSⁱ

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Abstract:

Family is the only institution that provides a general and important field in the modern society. The world is becoming more and more individualized yet more communicative and social with the impact of the media. Having both the commonality and privacy, the family setting provides a substructure to perform and practice the first important steps of life for any individual. The fullness of the family members or the lack thereof provide extra settings as to make it more complex; since family gatherings nowadays are becoming more and more impossible. General or individual celebrations of the family provide settings such as Thanksgiving Day, Mothers' day or Father's day assisting the protection of certain values in a worldwide platform.

These concepts surround the individuals not only in the society and in real life but also in media and virtual reality. Selling directly or indirectly to the family and realizing the importance of the family concept, the media suffers from the traditional sense of family spending time together, doing mass screenings in front of TV set as everyone used to once upon a time. Because, in this type of monitoring, individuals have the chance to reach and activate multiple messages and use other interactive tools. Yet, today's individuals have almost completely abandoned with collective tracking habits, developing and enriching their interests and increasing ownership of technological equipment such as iPad, tablets, computers, cell phones and other equipment. In the meantime, traditional television channels keep on representing the family in different ways sometimes united, sometimes separated or at times contradicting each other. This study focuses on how the concept of family is presented in the media in general terms, and whether such a family structure overlaps with the general community structure. The study focuses on the last five years since television broadcasts and television commercials are thought to have an important role in the way the family reflects the preservation of the existence and value of the family and its appropriation for future generations. The paper provides an analysis of the family types

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presented in the screen, discusses their representational function and compares and contrasts them with those clusters of the real society.

Keywords: family, media, television, advertisement, child, representation

1. Introduction

The nuclear family is considered as the base of the society, as the smallest unit, the building block, and the most valuable treasure that must be protected. Society is an organic body made up of families that are similar or unlike each other. When something happens to the family, society is also affected. The stronger the family is, the healthier and more conscious the society becomes. Society could be healthy, peaceful, happy, productive, and creative only if the families are so.

In various periods, community structures have placed the family in very different positions, and have greatly emphasized blood relation, religion, family affiliation, family unity, and unity with the society. Yet, today's socio-economic and situational approaches place the family in a highly ineffective and passive position, attributing it only the function of consumption. However, every family has its own dynamics and implements its own rules. The limitations prevent the mobility of the family with various boundaries and without mobility; the family could not apply its own rules. However, as with everything that has changed over time, the family undergoes a change in itself and enriches or replaces some of the core values with the new ones. Instead of obstructing, ignoring or stopping mobility, it is possible to ensure that the values of the past are transferred to the future before they vanish. The new generations would be the ones deciding which the old values would be taken care of and which of the new values would be paid attention to and implemented into the traditional structure. Thus, the nature of the society and the criteria for family structure would be changing constantly.

Apart from the family and its dynamics, the concept of media is changing every single minute. It's becoming very strategic, political, huge and separate world. On one hand, the media is constantly in development; making up new themes, concepts, fashions, designs and constructions under the name of new media but on the other hand, it helps people to change their lives, attitudes, life styles or expectations.

This partial or whole change of media finds new ways of producing materials, creating new presentation styles, providing new products, making it all different from the past. Not only the content but also the context and channels are changing rapidly; thematic, individualized and a highly liquid media is flowing all around the world. Whereas the traditional main stream media is making all the old fashioned styles live longer, the new generation also is captured through high speed, variations, interactions and virtual communities. Creating the desire to be a part of it, being represented or visualized somehow or becoming one of the specified group, the individuals find themselves in a kind of betterment setting, increasing their level of digital literacy as to

interact 24 hours continuously without missing a single message and sending thousands of them.

Social media permits the youngsters to take part in the activities even if they cannot really take part in it but rather puts them into a position of visualized, accepted and active citizens of these new groups. A life could change via an instant message or an email or an Instagram photo. The minute details of consumption and production handling all the energy and dedication to stay alive in such a world requires a lot of time and effort. Yet, the individuals and society are more than ready to make such sacrifices. This type of media brings up the new intergenerational, interdependent and global citizenship covering every individual, providing them new identities and new independency areas whereas somehow limiting them without permitting them to live the position in which they were structured. Freedom might be interpreted as implementing ways of the increasing the choices, variations of the television channels, changing rules of media ownership, opportunities for accessibility and multiple identities, making everyone a participant of this new and rich world.

People are now not only labeled as the audiences but also they become the producers, managers, distributors, disseminating the information in hand, even they become the ones having barter engagements not simple audiences just like in the past. The media implements life styles through the advertisements of their own philosophy. They implement messages into these wisely made up ads. However, these ads and messages are not consumed as these were considered to be somewhat more important as in the past decades. Once strolling around these texts stroll around almost forever. Since all the texts are now open texts in the 21st century, children and youngsters are thrilled about the innovations as well as the speed and dissemination of the information. On one hand the family dynamics change very quickly and they do not concentrate on the media as in the good old days. But on the other hand they have their own media in their hands now that means they become a part of it so easily and they value media more than anything else, more than their parents, educators or teachers, social rules or traditions. Not only the context but also the content is important for them. Even if they consume the messages in its bulk forms, they differentiate the meaning of a single word or they are aware of changing of a single color tone.

Apart from their level of awareness, they also become very addicted to the media and the medium that if they need to spend a few hours without internet or cell phones, they struggle with identity problems as if somebody underestimated their value or didn't bother acknowledging their existence.

According to the statistics, Turkey seems to be doing very well when the use of internet is considered to be one of the top 20 countries with its around 82 million population and 2700% of internet growth by 2018 whereas it is 1012% for the rest of the world (<https://www.internetworldstats.com/top20.htm>). Also, regarding the internet penetration rate to the population, it is around 69.6% (<https://www.internetworldstats.com/stats9.htm>) as a EU candidate country which was only 58% just last year (<http://www.internetlivestats.com/internet-users-by-country/>) and that means almost 56 million people in the country make use of their facebook

accounts. Over half of the world's population seems to be online now, with the latest data showing that nearly *a quarter of a billion* new users came online for the first time in 2017. Statistics prove that Africa has seen the fastest growth rates, with the number of internet users across the continent increasing by more than 20 % year-on-year (<https://wearesocial.com/us/blog/2018/01/global-digital-report-2018>). That means, we're social. That means they follow each other and decide what they like or dislike in less than a second. Their decision making strategies change a lot during the last decade.

Yet, this type of communication has nothing to do with the family communication where you might feel the soft and warm minutes shared with the family members. This brings forth a rather synthetic type of communication making it rather generalized yet more anonymous. The number of the people in contact appears to be reaching to somewhat top numbers in their contact list, even having a kind of communication with the ones they haven't even met before but in turn they almost give up their sharing with their own family members.

That means on one hand the media is recovering the people in many different ways but on the other hand it causes more estrangement even within the smallest unit of the society.

The parents in general lack the attention and care the children need due to the heavy work of the metropolitan cities. That's why the children lacking the parents' attention when they require might develop a tendency to be more in the media not only because it triggers their attention and learning desires but also media amuses them more than their parents. Whenever they reach to the level of purchasing their own goods they make up their own decisions. With this new generation of Z the new kids have interesting tendencies rather different from the earlier generations.

They also care for the medium that's why they pay more to watch a 4D version of the film with special glasses to feel themselves more in the action. They value the brands and functions more than any other generation. This reaches to such a peak that they may lose their self-confidence and may attack to the others or commit suicide if they cannot reach their expectations. Sometimes we hear news about the death of a young person due to the continuous energy they devoted to a program, a computer game or an online event.

The media attendance takes so much time that they forget to feed themselves and do not realize their lack of energy up to the moment they faint or die. This screen attendance reaches to such a dangerous point that, the people checking their e mail box only twice a day in the past now continuously keep an eye on their message boxes. Even if it sounds more and more normal such a freedom of communication for the sake of giving their right arms for a few more minutes in front of the screen was not normal just half a decade ago.

This kind of a captive life, as if chained to oars could bring a different type of humanity learned directly through the screens instead of the family or others in the society. In this new world of screens, everything should be presented through the screen; otherwise, people would never ever notice it. That's why nowadays parents find themselves calling their children for a meal even if they are in their just next door

rooms. This kind of a generation has nothing to do with the rules, parents, and traditions and imitate the ones they've never come across in real life, taking them as role models or idols. The penetration of the media is such a success in that case, having a huge impact on the followers and guiding them in the best possible way of selling them the things in the way they plan.

When such a density of consumption is not provided by the society or the family, the ones would be keeping up with the old traditional media, but the information gap between the advantaged group and disadvantaged group would be even greater than expected since the media is adding more and more into the core every minute. In fact, the new generation should neither follow the media blindly nor be bereft of the innovations and media, with fears, concerns and worries. When they feel that they lack such a stream of information they either reject it with a kind of anger and dissatisfaction or develop a pseudo neglect to such a novice form of life. Sometimes they accept information at face value, without further questioning or considering the possible risks even without regarding if they really need it or not. Under all these circumstances they never look like they internalize the factors as to adopt or retcon them or renew or shape for possible future usage. This mere acceptance is also as dangerous as neglect.

2. Aim and Methodology

The family is the only institution that provides a general and important field in the modern society. The world is becoming more and more individualized yet more communicative and social with the impact of the media. Having both the commonality and privacy, the family settings provide a substructure to perform and practice the first important steps of life for any individual. The fullness of the family members or the lack thereof provide extra settings as to make it more complex since family gatherings nowadays are becoming more and more impossible.

General or individual celebrations of the family provide settings such as Thanksgiving Day, Mothers' day or Father's day assisting the protection of certain values in a worldwide platform. These concepts surround the individuals not only in the society and in real life but also in media, and in virtual reality.

Selling directly or indirectly to the family and realizing the importance of the family concept the media suffers from the traditional sense of family spending time together, gathering around the television set as everyone used to once upon a time. Because, in this type of monitoring, observing and modelling, individuals have the chance of reaching and activating multiple messages and consequently use other interactive tools.

Yet, today's individuals have almost completely abandoned with collective tracking habits, developing and enriching their interests and increasing ownership of technological equipment such as iPad, tablets, computers, cell phones and other channels.

However, the main problem here is that even if all these changes seem to appear all of a sudden, the traditional media, especially, television channels and newspapers

keep on presenting and representing the family in the same way. Yet, the family now changed a lot in different ways: sometimes united, sometimes separated or contradicting with each other, unique family types also appeared.

This study focuses on how the concept of family is presented in the media in general terms and whether such a family structure overlaps with the general community structure. The study focuses on the examples covered within the last five years since television broadcasts and television commercials are thought to have an important role on the way the family reflects the preservation of the existence and value of the family and its appropriation for future generations. The paper analyses the family types presented in the screen, discusses the representational function of them if still valid, compares and contrasts them with those clusters of the real society.

3. Findings

In order to see the representations of family, specifically a channel appealing to the general tendencies of the society is chosen. This specific channel was not the one dealing with the local values or news but rather having a more modern sense as to be closer to the globalization ideas. All the advertisements broadcasted were recorded for six months and the family image reflected in these advertisements was coded regarding the type of family handled in the advertisement.

Out of many other ads, the ones with the family were in fact somewhat restricted. Except a few new examples, the ones referring to the concept of family were making use of the old, traditional family values neglecting the changes within the family system or the new paradigms of the childhood and families.

The findings of the paper could be summarized as such; the advertisements still produce the traditional values of the past rather than the new ones. The advertisements try to reach the family, aiming to affect them and get some desired type of consumer behaviors. Yet, the family types reflected and depicted in the commercials are rather old fashioned ones and these are in fact hard to appeal to the modern structured families. In most cases, the demographics, the structure, the tendencies of people change very rapidly due to the mobile technologies and economic life forcing people to be mobile and far away from each other. However, the presented family structure in the television commercials still represent the family as a unique and isolated way as to be together frequently in every occasion. This brings up the contradiction between the advertising techniques as well as the dissemination of information, modelling the figures or marketing the goods.

3.1 Representation of Family in Advertisements

Whereas the advertisements represent more of the idealized family life there seems to be different ways of representation regarding the society.

3.1.1 Ideal World - Ideal Family

Advertisements re-produce some certain concepts and attitudes, behaviors as to affect the audience making them believe that this idealized world is possible. Most people believe that advertisements only concentrate on certain products. However, it is a well-known fact that the products are secondary when it comes to the expectations, life styles, and philosophy of the commercials to be sold through the advertisements. In other words, the products are just the implementations of such a life style which means a larger concept to be sold. Once, the audience agrees upon to “become” somewhat different in a larger scale only then we may assume that they will develop the habit of buying the things related to that new world.

In this respect, the advertisements present an idealized world. Sterilized from problems, discussions, happy and rich. The individuals can do whatever they want in such a paradise but they choose the certain product to solve their nominal problems. Thus, the audience, generally cannot afford to get everything presented through the commercial but s/he can afford just a little part of it: That is the advertised product. To feel the similar happiness and richness, the people would like to be a part of the paradise represented on screen. Even if the commercials seem to be advertising just a single product in a very limited time, the main target is to develop and shape the values, styles, attitudes and hobbies they sell. Basically, the concrete products they seem to be selling are the objects of consumption, but what they actually offer us mainly consists of values. Whatever value you are willing to pay for is entirely dependent on the social and societal context and is linked to economic and educational opportunities, and cultural climate.

Advertisements sell a conceptual domain, a dreamland, an inaccessible, unattainable concept. So, in advertising, the emergence, existence or absence of a child or family, like all other values, is not very much related to the real world. However, our imagery, our mobilized world of virtual reality stemming from backgrounding these advertisements interprets it and compliments what it finds in the real world reciprocal. For example, in advertisements, the family is always presented in an idealized environment, in a wonderful, happy, amusing, caring, harmonious and understanding manner. Since visuals are known to be more intense and more permanent in memory, usually only smooth music accompanies such a sweet atmosphere. Rather than the seen or experienced items in the commercials, it is neither what you give or introduce nor how you put it into a context. It is rather how you make your audience feel. Thus, it's necessary to talk about the cumulative effect of such an imaginary world they create beyond the individual products presented in advertisements.

The ideal family is usually a nuclear one. In most cases, they have a single child. 1/3 of the families are represented in the form of a boy or a girl. The other type is more futuristic, having two children. In ideal days, occasions, religious or important celebration days, the elder parents, uncles and big family members are all shown. These films make up about 2% of the advertisements. In ideal world – ideal family representations, the family members are all shown together, doing things together.

3.1.2 Family Members used as a part of the family

In most cases, the family as a whole is not seen in the advertisements. Depending on the product, the related member of the family is reflected with it, but the main idea is to reach to the whole family. The presentation of the family in commercials is carried with a couple of perspectives. The advertisers regard the family as a large umbrella, knowing that they can guarantee their sales and profits. When this large umbrella, accept their products they may sell it to anyone under this umbrella. So, referring to the system rather than the individuals requiring the products makes more sense. Audiences like it as well since nobody would like to face the loneliness in real life and instead prefer to be under the same umbrella with the other beloved ones even if this is just a dream. Advertisers are also aware of the kind of pressure that the family applies in their own way, such as public pressure, peer pressure, etc., To them, it doesn't really matter which of these members are captured for this specific product because they want to handle each family member through an institutional approach and they much less care about which one of the members of the family has taken over.

3.1.3 Pseudo Family – Targeting Children

From a different perspective, it is quite striking that even if all advertisements seem to be targeting adults, they provide children representations. In their scenarios, whether necessary or unnecessary, this placement and implementation of children into almost every position is thought to be motivating the future consumers, contributing to the brand development and raising brand awareness for the next generation. Finally, the creation of an environment of health, trust and peace that is provided by the family make up messages that appeal to the spectators' pathos, and the desire to take care of the kids and future. Even if it seems that most of the buying decisions are made through the intellectual questioning period, it has also been proved that for most people buying decisions are made emotionally. The brain minimizes the choices and yet the minimal differences usually stand more on the emotional side rather than the intellectual one. In this case, since the viewer is in pursuit of the images of his individual life, he attempts to repeat or recreate his happiness in his memory rather than seeking to question the reality of this image. As a result, the advertisements, in the context of awareness of the efficiency and functioning of the family institution, directly or indirectly prepare messages for this institution, interpret them as a consumption triangle consisting of parents and children, and in this context they are actually marketing the concept of family as a bestselling idea.

3.1.4 No Family but the Concept of the Family

In some cases, the family never appears physically in the commercials, not even a part of it. It is the concept of family that is represented. In a way, this is an approach accompanying the concept of family since, being a family does not always require the family members to be together physically. The values attributed to the family could be somewhat more deeper and abstract rather than making it obvious or concrete. In some ads, for example in MNG Cargo Company ads, the family is not seen in the screen,

instead it's in the form of ducks, passing through the road. The motorcycled courier waits for them, giving them the right of way. Observing this, the knitting old woman by the side of the road, establishes a kind of trust in him and states a wish to send the astronaut costume for her grandson who lives in a far away city. Even if there seems to be no family in the ads, the implied concept of family stands still as a well-used metaphor just like in most of the advertisements.

3.2 Representation of Family in Television Programs

The concept of media covers more than just television. Apart from the advertisements, there are other programs that seem not to target the consumption of the media or products aimed at the family institution. Even if you watch the news, the family is being followed very closely and what happens to the family is being discussed. The main difference at this point could be noticed through the emergence of print media, visual media and internet media as well as the social media. While the print media presents the most unfavorable, most detailed state of the family-related events, the internet media is in pursuit of selling the single lines even asking the questions that the answers were already been known and leaving behind more questions to make the audience follow them to question the rest.

Television does not only broadcast the advertisements but other programs such as news and serials, panels and competitions, etc. Thus, the representations of the family in each different media structure provide contradictory messages to the other media.

In commercials, idealized family concepts are presented more. On one hand, trying to draw us a so-called happy picture in which the concept of family is introduced in an important and idealized way, putting it in a higher valued position to keep it sacred as it was in the past. Yet, on the other hand, in the news and serials sections, the family relations are made more grifted, the big secrets are kept throughout many years and everyone in the family lies to each other. In that case it is necessary to emphasize that we cannot find a real, intimate, healthy and peaceful family relationship in any part of the media. Yet, the audience never questions this contradictory presentations. The serials are mainly relying upon the same structure, the change of identity at some point in life and the complications carried out because of such a chance. One might easily react to the repeated patterns of local serials constantly formulating it in similar identity change stories.

It might be a bit misleading to think that audiences are really influenced by commercials. Not even true users of the products are effected by the commercials and make their mind up to purchase the products when they watch it on television.

It can also be argued that advertisements are not targeting only a certain type of consumer and that they do not aim to choose sending messages to each different class of the demographics in the society since they do not display realistic measures in terms of living standards. So it would be wrong to say that the effect of the advertisements is spreading over a wide range or it is almost instantaneous. However, advertisements

play an extremely important role in the creation, design and presentation of the concepts.

Either the advertisements or the other types of television programs provide the audience a kind of world and life style what they can reach and make up in years to come, while enabling viewers to design what kind of world they dream of or how they can make it possible in future. Here they perhaps put forward the standards of living, the first quality products or second quality of products, alternatives or many other concepts. The futuristic attitude displayed by advertisements allows them to move more deeply into memory and penetrate into the depths of life with more lasting, more efficient messages, despite the view that dramatic sequences do not pay much attention to realities of today's family. It is important to emphasize that ads are more important than the other type of television programs since they have a short, effective, colorful and repeatable structure. It is important to remember that commercials are short and not much is questioned since there isn't sufficient time to do so. However, the serials provide us settings in which we come across with the characters, dialogues, actions and there is ample time to question them all. That's why these programs have less effect on the audience since the audience is actively thinking of it whereas the commercials provide settings without questioning.

3.3 The Concept Family is a Selling One

The concept of the family may not be appropriate for all advertisements because the family is a little fragile, perhaps fringe and distant concept in terms of advertisers. It is much easier for them to divide the consumer block into rather individualized pieces and seize it one by one. The family, on the other hand, is a compromise, an integration, so that regardless of the objects produced or the services provided, it is considered to be a much simpler approach to reaching individuals one by one than integrating the complicated structure of the family.

There are differences between ads targeting the family and portraying family in its ideal way as to reach to the target. Advertisements targeting the family will find it sufficient for the family to adopt what they market as a product, even if they are the family members themselves. In the case of advertisements positioning "the family as a setting" to make use of the product, there is a desire to benefit from the characteristics of the family concept. A much more comfortable, rich and wide market can be achieved if the communicative characteristics of trust, health, hygiene, love and respect reflected by the context of family provide a harmonious congruence with the product being marketed.

It could also be claimed that the serials are not actually for family consumption due to their divisive structure. The soap opera type serials covering women mostly, youth serials aiming for young people and adventure and action series appealing to men are targeting different kinds of broadcasting units having certain and separate targets via the screen entertainment. Advertisements on the other hand not aiming certain plots stand by the crossroads of all the members functioning almost as a meeting point for the family. Advertisements providing an informative, relaxing and

entertaining environment that everyone could join uninterruptedly can be especially effective with the humor factor that they have in the forefront.

It can be seen that the advertisements have a certain calendar. In certain periods of time, the sale of certain types of products is fore fronted, such as the start of the school semester is the right time for school shopping, and advertisements that prioritize holiday spending while vacationing are on the agenda. In addition to basic topics such as home, car, and bank credit, they can provide information on white goods, new products, and summarize efforts to create markets for specific days. Social concepts and gatherings such as religious holidays, festivals and concepts that are seen as the main marketplace such as Mother's Day, Father's Day, Valentine's Day are being juggled hand to hand with the advertisements in a certain way.

Whereas not considered to be very important under normal conditions, family concepts are transformed into an element of consumption on such special occasions, and they are sometimes able to be dedicated a representation to carry on a more emotional dimension. Especially during Ramadan and religious festivals, when there is a family together, the priority is given to items often presented and expressed as a consumption phenomenon which is frequently emphasized in advertisements.

At all other times of the year, the media, which mainly focuses on core family representation, as part of the family as mothers or fathers, emphasizes wider family representation in such special moments trying to keep different generations together. In doing so, sometimes messages having densely emotional sentiments and idealized representations as to make it possible to preserve this 'default' family structure.

In this case, a dilemma appears. On one hand, media imposes a pseudo reality such as a crowded big family cadre for the continuity of the series to come, the crowd of player cadres and the development of the series characters. Yet, on the other hand we are in the process of seeing the fact that such family structures are rapidly decreasing and evolving towards the nuclear family in real life. Nevertheless, especially in the serials, more than the individualism, collective matters are foregrounded and there is a return to inter-generationalism, different generations living in the same home, especially given the livelihood conditions and the care provided to children as well as the economic conditions.

Nevertheless, when life expectancies, economic and educational factors are linked to technology, it is inevitable that more generous opposition of generational conflicts would occur. The values have changed rapidly and we are at a time when a dominant view of consumer culture gains more and more importance. The media is at a point where it is constantly arguing that existing values should be replaced by new and more pragmatic values. Neither old-fashioned protection nor precious kinship is known to media audiences, nor is it afforded the ability to benefit from this joy in the face of innovation. Advertisements are much more preliminary because they aim to consume as much as they are short and effective.

The studies conducted on yearly television ads determined that out of the whole ads the advertising of food products is mainly occupied a huge bulk among all the others. Among all other advertisements, food ads account for 38%, followed by

personal care products and cosmetics at a rate of 12%. Bank advertisements, which are thought to determine economic decisions more positively, have an 11% share. It is not surprising to see that some of the members of the family or family are mainly in food products when certain types of activities such as food and drink are thought to be activities with family members and friends and groups of friends. Nevertheless, despite the fact that personal care products offer more individual use, advertisements appear to be fostered in social interaction environments.

Figure 1: Ads Coverage

For the ads examined, the findings could be stated as follows. It is not very functional to repeat the concept of family as a concept that is "remembered" from the days of social importance such as Ramadan and Eid al-Fitr. Society always needs to cycle the need for the family. In order to maintain the family factor as valuable as ever, the environment of love, respect, care, consideration and importance should be shared with all the parties even if these all seem to have a symbolic type of expressions and limited to the special occasions. Of course, the attachment of family images to every product is also not a way to work with each product. Then there may be a risk of encountering unnecessary normalization and neglect.

Hygiene-related products (Liquid hand soap or toothpaste) usually display a family-friendly appearance. It is emphasized that the responsibility of each individual of the family is to be clean. Parent - child trio are shown during shopping, together and hand washing. It is thought to be a positive representation. Similarly, children's brushing habits can be considered as a positive image of family brushing. However, it can be questioned, for example, how the connection of picnics or outdoor fun to the family is established in the images of socialization associated with tooth brushing.

Generally, for juveniles and children's food, such as chocolate and chocolate product advertisements, subliminal sexual codes or associations are used that children cannot understand. This is an extremely harmful approach.

Certain types of advertisements are loaded with certain values, which in time can lead to misleading by producing prejudices, and standardized patterns. For example, in detergent advertisements, the child is presented at a point that is constantly polluting the subject.

In advertisements with young children, parents are usually kept on the agenda. This perspective, given the assumption that it is the mother's responsibility to look after the child, due to their ease of attraction, also reinforces their loneliness and strengthens the idea that this burden is placed on them at the social level, while securing the authority of their mother in child rearing, nutrition and care. Meanwhile, visual, linguistic and intellectual discrimination between girls and boys continue even if most of them are exemplified with the ads of diapers and food.

4. Conclusion

This study focuses on how the concept of family is presented in the media in general terms and whether such a family structure overlaps with the general community structure. The study focuses the last five years, since television broadcasts and television commercials are thought to have an important role in the way the family reflects the preservation of the existence and value of the family and its appropriation for future generations.

The paper provides an analysis of the family types presented in the screen, discusses their representational function, and compares and contrasts them with those clusters of the real society. How these images are scattered is analyzed through the 12T's approach, inspired by the A Six-T's Approach to Content-Based Instruction by Stoller & Grabe by 1997 and developed into as a film analysis technique by Pembecioğlu by 2012. Each T stands for a different perspective checking the quality of the given text. The main aim, following the coherence and cohesion of the text is to reach to a kind of formula exposing or deciphering the content, function and position of the required unit researched for. Today, used in many film analysis research papers 12T's approach makes it possible to make a content analysis to find out how the mermaid images are depicted for various purposes in highly different ways. Namely Theme, Topic, Text, Thread, Task, Transfers & Trends, Transition, Thinking, Tailoring, Taking Risks, Technology, Transmedia. These T's put forward how the narrative is shaped and what it includes apart from the main issue.

Depending upon the types of advertisements making use of the family image pretends to plan the life style, expectations and standards of a family in a culture. The messages exposed to the society in a way maintains the limits and shapes the rules on the way to conduct the family budget and expenses. Even if the social status, economic income and cultural values wouldn't be the same, through advertisements, a homogenous world is created so that all the dreams and expectations become equal in

this virtual world. In other words, you should be happy when you could purchase any of these advertised products as to reach to the level of happiness they perform through the screens.

4.1 Elders

It is a little vague who represents family in advertisements featuring family. For example, concepts such as mother-in-law, father-in-law, bride, groom (detergent advertisements, comparing which one is better or food items related to whose dish is tastier – because she used the right brand, etc.) are presented in advertisements. These old fashioned models are used to criticize the modern applications or new ways but it is always the new generation that prevails. Of course depending upon the nature and dignity of the brand advertised sometimes it is the older part that gains the advantageous situation, still standing against the new brands, etc. These implemented members of the family usually act to question the product, process or the decision. Such little sweet competitions are always brought to the agenda. The producers and advertisers believe that the society needs such advertisements and they would like to associate their product with respect, love and understanding among family members, so that the audience experiences an emotional attachment rather than meeting just a showy photo.

Such sweet competition environments in the family may sometimes be presented in the form of mother-children and sometimes father-child relationships. For example, a father or son who transform the living room into a basketball court may bet for a package of food, and the scene may change up to the point that the child is faced with violent attacks or flying slippers since the father cannot tolerate losing the game. In the same ad, through the cut montage approach as the the product is introduced to the audience, the family members consume the product separately and individually in each frame. At this point, it is emphasized that the product can be separated as well as the family and in fact it is a danger for the family unity.

4.2 Children

Even if there are some rules preventing children to take part in the commercials, children can be shown in advertisements as fillers of the situation. For example, we come across the child when they are usually helping with housework and sometimes with farm work. In return, they are also shown as to consume the product presented to them as a reward of their hard work. This type of presentations is alright and there is not much to criticize. Having a share in the family work, family involvement in household affairs is a very positive approach, but it is sometimes exaggerated and children are used in the advertisements of the products that they are not connected to in any way. Products such as washing machines, tumble dryers or automobiles, the presence of children in advertisements is seen as a guarantee of the continuity of these brands.

There are also images in the advertisements about promoting the creativity of the child in the family. However, these children are presented as the ones in the form of a

team work in an environment where they are with other children. They are presented with the words such as "I want to be a famous pop singer" and act like singing. And the mother brings the food for them so that they are rewarded and supported. It is believed that this kind of a family support and feeding the child in the right way is seen as the first step to the success. Yet, this seems to be somewhat fairly unethical practice in since these children can lead to wrong role model choices. Similarly, in a baby diaper ad, the famous baby meets her fans on the day of signing. All mothers who take their babies to the event also participate in this activity. That means they become a part of a larger group using similar products, making smart choices.

The coexistence of children and their mothers can be seen side by side in pseudo daily environments of the advertisements whereas they almost never are in real life, and they are shown continuously together, at home, at a sports center, and at school. But the audience knows that family members are not really that much involved with their children. Moreover, it is also absolutely reminded with animated characters used that it is in fact an unreal environment, even in the most important moments of life. In other words, unrealistic childhood world is expected to be believed by both children and adults. Moreover, in such advertisements, a so-called competition is often exhibited as inappropriate behavior, such as hijacking and taking, stealing or pursuing the product that is often beloved and cannot be shared with the others even with the family members. It is not very pleasant especially with food products taken or stolen from family members and this type of presentation of the family is not appropriate.

4.3 Elders & Children

It seems that children and grandparents are constantly performing unusual acts in situations where being a parent is usually linked to economic problems and humor. Advertisements never mention what it is like being a family in real life and the extensions of this concept. They only refer to slices of life and specific importance is given to the desired actions or reflections. For example, once the family is mentioned, only the parents and the children are shown or the children's eating habits are presented through the focusing cameras but the concept of family should not be portrayed in that way and should not be downgraded up to those little slices. It is also necessary to emphasize the importance of understanding others, and understanding between family members and solidarity. Among all ads analyzed, the concept of 'sister/brother' is presented only visually in three ads. In one of the ads, these are depicted as two sisters supporting each other even if they get old in later ages of life. The other example is about two brothers having a kind of competition, criticism and offended attitude in between. A girl and a boy appeared to be the brother and sister in a diaper advertisement

There are also advertisements placing little siblings with little age differences, and these kids usually consume the different versions of the same product. Only in one of the advertisements of some snack products, the concept of an auntie appears. However, the food looks so delicious that young children cannot stand the temptation of it even if they were responsible to deliver it to their aunts, and in conclusion they sit

by the side of the road and eat it. This also seems to be an example of the sacrifices that should be made for family members are lacked, yet the young generation has no courage or patience for that. However, the good hearted aunt, meeting the youngsters with an empty plate, takes the situation in a different way and refills their lunch box again with the same delicious product. As a result, the misbehavior of the children is being rewarded even if it is due to a misunderstanding. Meanwhile, the product is being launched as "new pleasure of the family". Similar mottos are used in different products ranging from being the "tomato family" to include the different kinds of canned foods, to the "snack family" to include the richness of the products. The motto "family-style flavor" covers the traditional taste of family and importance of sharing. Another motto "family size happiness" is used to refer to the size of the products. The other concepts implemented into the family include, for family taste, for enjoyment of your family, for your family (in general) and for family safety.

There is a misunderstanding that when humor is involved, it is believed that everything you portray would be accepted without a single question. However, it is the actions that the mind remembers. Yet, especially in advertisements, the family environment is often associated with food trafficking and the family is portrayed only when they're eating together around the same big table. However, showing family members sitting at the table for lunch or dinner, smiling at each other, or for example eating pasta on the same plate add neither to the family concept nor to the brand. One other thing to be discussed here is perhaps presenting a Turkish family eating Italian pasta in a pasta commercial film and launching it as a "True Italian flavor for your family".

4.4 Ethics

In some of the advertisements, there is a kind of disapproval of the family. These kinds of insubordinate behaviours, such as doing the opposite of what's being said or stealing the parent's / kid's portion of the food could be the examples of a 'modern' family. In such families, the kids are seen as the dudes or equivalent members of the parents just like any other friend, etc. Yet the behaviours within the family limits may change from being untidy to telling a lie, from providing misinformation to hard critics with sarcasm.

Sometimes, it's not the resistance to the family but to the whole society or the rules, values. In such cases, the family members have a little shock and depending upon the new trend, they seem to be accepting the challenge. In this case, it's either the young parents siding by the new generation with much more understanding or the old parents accepting the new circumstances as to go with the stream even if it costs them a great change in this new way. This kind of obedience is only applicable in the family gatherings, through the family pressure. The father for example, even if it is a bit expensive agrees with the idea of buying a new car, a nice holiday or a new house. He knows that he'll be excluded from the family dynamics if he doesn't. The little boy tells a lie to the mother to prevent his position in the eyes of the mother. He pretends to be

successful even if he loses a match. Understanding the situation, the mother offers him a new milk brand and helps him to become successful.

In a different example, the poor father having not much money to take the kids to a nice (Bairam) holiday hides behind a couch. The bank finds him there and offers a new credit card to solve his problem. So the father becomes the hero of the family. One other advertisement shows the mother stealing the yoghurt of her son, feels sorry, so that she buys four caps next time to be shared by the parents and kids.

The boy teasing with the father about the latest basketball match finds out how much he's in the sports and discovers that the depth of this knowledge could only be possible with the cheap internet company offers.

The new bride, who has to dance in the wedding in a certain traditional style, shouts out loud for due to thirst and there appears the new ice-tea brand as opposed to the traditional drinks.

4.4 Gatherings

It's important how the family is gathered and portrayed and what they do in commercials in general. Because family appears in different types of products but the family concept is the same in general. In this respect, the family type we see in this commercial or in another one, is just parts of the same thing.

Some products contribute to that concept, some damage it through misbehaviors. These images depicting the family are actually little fragmented images of a larger photograph. In each ad, we see the different façade of the same concept. In majority of advertisements, the family is shown to consume a certain brand in a dining environment. It is noteworthy that only one of the advertisements analyzed portrays the family when they are just having fun. This atmosphere, depicting different generations enjoying time together, unfortunately offers to an idealized fun environment that many families can not realize or actualize due to the economic constraints.

Little kids appearing in advertisements for the products not really appealing to children are used in a twofold way as to make the product more attractive to adults by the sweetness created with the children's voices and assets, as well as implementing memories into children as the audience is possible future users.

4.5 Gender

The sexist viewpoint between male and female is presented as a competitive element in many advertisements. There is a continuous competition atmosphere ranging from the brewing of tea to making decisions for all kinds of actions.

What is lacked in most of the advertisements is that, it should be emphasized that the generations may have different values not contradicting each other, but somehow these values should be protected and taken care of by the new generations since we cannot put them aside and ignore all those people who still stick to those values. It might be a fringe example but in some advertisements, the consumption of children's products by adults can be seen as a clear indication of this situation. Such

products emerge at the moments when children and adults have fun together and 'pamper' them.

4.6 Nuclear Family & Large Family

The family situation can sometimes turn into a crowded meeting environment, and it is emphasized how important it is to share happiness with big and fancy table parties that family members or other relatives participating. Even if these happy moments are usually presented as situations in modern families, it is clear that in these settings turning to women's help with the tableware, accompanied with the dishwasher or detergent conversations actually are not much far from the traditional patterns.

When it comes to intra-family communication, it is also important to know who is talking to whom and how. Regarding the family members to be in communication with each other in advertisements, analysis prove that the mother and the son talk is more frequently depicted. In these conversations, what we usually experience is that the mothers are successful in speaking the same language of the young person despite the generation gap. The examples could be referred as Selpak toilet paper with its "give five" action, Beko washing machine: "This match does not end here, goes into extra-time", Honey peanut butter: "I'm after power".

Concentrating on the generation gap, in one of the advertisements, the old lady being a taxi driver replies the customer, "Okay boy, I got it". However, as in other advertisements, the older generation represents the old fashion people. In these ads, the driver moves even slower than they should, and the music accompanies them. The commercial depicting the honorable old lady with a glimpse of humor as lagging behind modernization, having a slow and frenzied mentality.

In another advertisement, a mother's importance in a child's life is explained in a long way through examples. Afterwards she learns through her new cell phone that her son expects baked semolina for dinner. Decorated with humorous elements she also learns more about her new GSM operator, providing her a new smart phone and cheap line to put her into a more communicative point to interact with her son more, the old fashioned mother smiles accepting that mothers need such "smart" presents to keep up with the new generation.

Family is also placed in the advertorial slots having longer sessions than the general advertisements. Usually these ones provide long introductions about a particular new product. In order to engage more of the family members for a longer period of time, the advertisements provide all the examples for the family members. For example, the product is used by the elders in the family, the product is used by the youngsters in the family, etc. Thus, the product is introduced two or more times concentrating on the features such as ease of use or its flexibility for all the family members. In that case, the decision of purchase for the item seem to be quite easy.

In the advertisements depicting large family gatherings around a table, the scene reflects all the joy and happiness of the participants around the table everyone talks to each other and the camera shows us their sincerity, closeness as well as happiness.

In these scenes, depictions of family include all the members, the cheerful environment where they eat and drink happily, perhaps rejoicing the good old day and have a nice enjoyable conversation with each other. In such a climate of mutual understanding, support and sharing, all of the food and things disappear and everything is degraded up to a product as if all of it was caused by the use of a product.

4.7 Special Days

When we consider that all advertisements analyzed are totally almost two and a half hours, yet, only about 10% of those ads portray the family image. And it can be said that only about 2% has a nice quality that strongly displays the family image in the way that it should be. Even when looking at the advertisements prepared specifically for Mother's Day, Father's Day and other festivals, we cannot expect a different picture. Two criteria have been taken into consideration for the evaluation of advertisements. All the ads broadcasted on 2014 on Fox TV channel were chosen and only the ads containing the family concept from the linguistic or visual point of view were included into the sample. The other sample is based on the category of awarded advertisements; the ads that received the Crystal Apple award in 2015 were also evaluated. The leading and strong companies of Turkey, the advertising films of the best brands involving the "family" concept were discussed and analyzed regarding how they positioned the family issues.

When we look at family related advertisements, we can see that there is a priority regarding the fathers and father figures. It can also be interpreted as a fact that as the breadwinner or head of the household, fathers are given priority instead of the general target audience as women and children. That means, fathers are also taking their share of ads through their payings for the products advertised [1].

One of the best brands in Turkey is AKBANK's Father's Day ad. Under the heading of "Father's Day", which was presented as a special day accompanied by the well-known song "You did it to yourself," and the audience was directed to certain types of consumption and habits, through hashtags #noneedmyson #noneedmydaughter in a "smart" way. In these serials, in each episode the fathers in fact buy their own gifts as if their sons or daughters had bought them and receive the presents after a nice ceremony. In these depictions, the father and son or the father and daughters are all alone except just one of them appears to have the mother figure accompanying the ceremony. It may be argued that the presented family concept does not cover much of Turkey and only depicts the middle and upper middle class, representing modern families following the innovations and core family theme.

In these ads, children who are 8-14 years old present their gifts to their fathers and the audience is provided visuals of the gift opening ceremonies whereas the implications include that the fathers must be strong and sulky, they do not react emotionally, the temperature, meaning, and sanctity of the family are not valued that much but what matters is just the consumption values and economic troubles.

The advertisement of Turkish Airlines 'Dad and Team of experts' counts THY's services for children through their point of view on one hand and on the other hand, it

does not stop at comparing and contrasting their function with real paternal functions (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q1VsxcqE6xg>). This advertising film, which implements the integrated marketing principles, displays the privilege of flying with THY on the one hand and on the other hand celebrating the Father's day. In this context, the THY cabin team's approach to family warmth is at the forefront. It is a common practice and very meaningful attempt to associate the functions of some institutions with the concept of 'family'. In this commercial, animated visuals lead the audience to testify that İŞ BANKASI is shown as an institution just like a family [2].

Another advertisement portraying the father figure has a script that includes the family agency of TÜRK TELEKOM's device campaign advertisement and narrates the story over the father figure [3]. The 'conscious consumer' dad, taking care of, and being in touch with all the family members, keeps pace with the progressive innovative technology, shares his problems with his family members with his competent sales counselor even if he is linguistically and visually different from him. Afterwards everyone becomes happy including all his family members. Here, the fact emphasized is that the fatherly sharings with each family member, being sensitive to their happiness and needs is very important.

Providing the visibility of the family institution on to the screen is of course important, provided that it appears in a more positive and meaningful way. For example, high-income and educated husband and wife communication is a striking example. The couple communicates with each other in Garanti Bank ads, but they do not sit on the same breakfast table and speak with each other raising their voices, which offers us a very positive form of family communication. The woman who blames her husband for fear of technology and complains that her husband does not let her have her banking transactions. At the end she emphasizes that she is not as independent as she wishes [4].

In this controversial issue, representing a hot family struggle, the winning part is neither the man nor the woman but the technology and the bank. The dull, dimly lit colors used throughout the film are particularly noteworthy.

One other father's day ad is presented as a result of long and exhausting work with the children's focus group [5]. The combination of adult creativity with childhood creativity, purity and emotionality makes the composition extremely successful because it is based entirely on the concepts that the children express.

Similarly, the words for the mothers in the Carrefour s.a. commercial for Mother's Day are backed up not by the (un)realistic accompanying musical instruments, but with the message that everything the mothers want is in Carrefour s.a. [6]. Despite the dominant father figure in father's day advertisements, it is quite striking that these Mother's Day ads never encounter the mother figure in the middle nor in the end.

In another example of the ads, a mother image not being used in advertisements focusing on the anniversary is more noticeable. For example, in the vanguard of the industry, Profilo found that university students living away from their homes try to cope with their own problems. Yet, the use of music is very effective and is a touching traditional song [7]. At the end, the youngsters were able to create creative solutions to

their everyday problems while building their homes with 'high high hills'. Mixed with humor, traditions, maternal care and sentimentality; they tried to visualize how life could be in a house where there is no family environment without a mother. Though it is a bit strange, that all the mothers tried to be identified with a certain technological small household appliance and that no maternal figures were used in the film.

It is not as much of a struggle for mothers to perceive themselves as the ones who consume a lot, with the company of the song 'Mazeretim Var' on Turkcell's anniversary day advertisement [8] for Mother's day. But this time, the depiction of the mother is frequently an annoying but boring one with unnecessary requests, who is rather protective and unnecessarily emotional, and arguable.

Vestel produced an advertisement of small household appliances. In these ads, the woman has a lot of thoughts and inquiries about her child, spouse, daily life, neighbors, neighbor's child, child's friends, etc. It shows how much the mothers care for all the others and how we, the society care for her. At the end, the mother is a samovar to make tea for all the beloved ones [9].

Advertisements for mothers, fathers or parents usually appear on such special days, mostly characterized by certain types of consumptions. This can be explained by the point of view that as a society we are becoming more and more consuming, rather than valuing the traditional aspects such as respect, love and value.

On the basis of these consumptions are small household appliances, modern products such as kitchenware, permanent and tangible products are introduced since these are well known innovative means for practical and modern kitchens. It would be important to notice that even if the advertisements and celebration ways seem to be modern, these advertisements reinforce the traditional roles in the society. "Mothers are always associated with the kitchenware products; let it be the modern ones."

In Vestel's advertisement, an integrated marketing example is used as the consumers could get discounted Pegasus tickets once Vestel's products are bought. In the ads, the woman runs towards the son and the son is waiting with his arms wide open assuming that the mother is running to him because of the love and happiness of the new present. However, the mother runs for the new kitchen appliance as to win another flight ticket.

As a more realistic mother-child relationship, advertisement Korkmaz brand seems to be focused entirely on the mother-child relationship without prioritizing their products [10]. It can be assumed that the gender theories are at work for this example again, that all the responsibilities of kitchen and household are given to the woman. Kamil Koç is presenting an imaginary mother who is not there during her pseudo-trip and emphasizing her sensitivity in her ad on Mother's Day [11] which aims to emphasize that services are offered for a mother-in-law image.

Even if hundreds of ads were analyzed there would seem to be many problems regarding the depiction of the family in ads. One of them is that "How should the communication be presented in ads to maintain the importance of the family and the family unity?"

There is no healthy aspect of the family representation presented in the media. There are artificial and objectionable aspects in each of the ads. It is inevitable to think that a publishing mentality that gives attention to presentation of the product is present. Instead, a simple and effective way of telling the story could be preferred rather than exaggeration or normalization of the pseudo situations. Allocating more space for ordinary people's daily stories would be more accurate and effective. In the ones presenting almost an equal balance for modern parenting, the objects of desire, such as a piece of food is going like hot cakes from one member to another. The family members are secretly stealing the product or eating them without sharing it with the others. In this case, the product is put into a position that the members of the family are not as valued as the product. This brings us to the materialistic values again. What's family for and what are the values of the family. In its traditional sense, the members of the family who make sacrifices for each other or share the last sip and break bread together now instead drink or eat it up selfishly.

Analysing the advertisements through 12T's approach, we have interesting findings. The 12T's approach is a way of analyzing the media and the texts through certain headlines such as Theme, Topic, Text, Thread, Task, Transfers & Trends, Transitions, Thinking, Tailoring, Taking Risks, Technology and Transmedia.

The **Theme** of family sells much in brands, commercials and even in sitcoms. Apart from being a large umbrella, the family as a theme covers more than the family such as the contradictions, the gender differences, the generation gap, modernity vs traditions, conversations and all kinds of communication outcomes. Thus, the family as a theme will be a granted space for most of the modern storytellers.

Regarding the **Topic**, any of these topics or some others might be available for the advertisements having family depictions. Once we consider the family as the main theme of these products, the umbrella term is family. Even in today's modern world family matters change a lot from one society to another, including the single parent families, single mom or single dad or single foster parents, not much details are displayed in the worlds of advertisements. No different couples are represented like homosexual fathers or mothers. In none of the parents seems to be divorced or remarried couples. No families living with their old or new children appear in the advertisements. No couples without kids were reflected in the ads. None of the children are living by themselves. All the families in the advertisements are happily married with children. The irony is that even though such families are so rare -even in this pseudo – world created in the advertisements- they attract the attention of the consumers and make them buy the product. In this case, it's not the product itself but the concept of family that sells.

The couples are usually the working ones and able ones. Mostly educated and self-confident people are starring in the ads. These are not the ones breathlessly running here and there to eke out or just meet each other at the weekends. Usually, the crowded families having breakfast together are dressed up as if it's a special day. It's not only the theme, the type of family represented in a false way but also the topic, how the family is positioned in the advertisements. In such situations no one is busy or anxious or in a

hurry. These people seem to have a lot of time to spend for a large breakfast and to smile at each other with happiness. The mother is usually responsible for the preparation of the food and the rest of the family seems to be helping her one way or another.

Regarding the **Text** cluster, most of the texts of these advertisements contain happy moments, such as a special celebration, the mother's day, the father's day, eid Mubarak or graduation ceremonies, marriages, etc. The people in the screen are not preoccupied; they are alert, conscious and ready to act. The texts also include three generations as to accompany the youngsters so that the values and traditional life style is emphasized.

Family theme is mostly used in many advertisements. But, in order to make up a family effect, you do not need to show the whole family or the parts of it. In this case, the **Threads** could be found in the details such as a smooth touch of a mother, a smile of a father, a permission given by the grannie, or a moment of tolerance by the grandpa, etc. The other details that could be contributing to the threads are the emotions added into the situation. Usually this is a setting everyone is meeting another with joy, shaking hands, exchanging presents etc. or sometimes it's the moment of missing or yearning. Whatever the desire, the expectations are of course fulfilled because of being a family. In some cases, the **Tasks** are shared by the family members or it's the task of the product to complete the happiness of the family. Sometimes it's the task of returning home, or finishing a school and bringing the joy of graduating into the family. Sometimes it's the food, having a nostalgic moment for family members. Whatever the task is, it's been performed successfully so that the audience could observe the satisfaction and buy the product when it comes to that.

The **Transfers and Trends** are allocated in the commercials, so that in most cases, the family touch would be a nice one except for a few cases regarding the deaths or being far from the beloved ones. The family members are depicted as the ones missing each other or thinking the same thing at the same time. The camera first shows the elderly mother for example and later the young mother preparing the meal in the same way, so that this is generalized as the traditional taste. The rituals, celebrations of a birthday or an Eid Mubarek refer not only to the family but also to the traditions. One other type of family depiction is the rebel against the family. If this is a new product making the utmost use of the new trends & technology etc. it could cause the values to turn upside down. The traditional wedding scene for example showing the bride and groom dancing together in the traditional style, the bride shouts out loud "Enough!" This could be accepted or interpreted not only as an ordinary thirst but also a revolt against the traditions and such rituals. The advertised item is the ice tea and one may easily guess the transfers and trends that might appear. These also bring together the **Transitions**, such as the competitions on making up which taste is better than the other, which one deserves to be the champion, etc. These transitions not only cover the differences and similarities but also have an important impact on the society. For example once you buy a juice extractor it means that you'll spare some time and money for fruit juice. The why, when and how would depend upon your choices but the main

thing is this transition. Similarly, once you have a coffee machine you also tend to buy a certain type of coffee to make use of your new item. These transitions effect the little tiny details of the general lifestyle, however, the main reason underlying these transitions is perhaps the family depictions you come across.

The transitions throughout the advertisements do not only effect the product sales but also changes the values, styles and standards of life. This would also affect the way of **Thinking** and perhaps the change of tastes. The thinking concept here refers to the evaluation of the whole system as well as the addictions, habits, preferences and expectancies. Thus, it's going to be the audience's decision requiring thinking.

Tailoring the details into the commercials is the creative way of the text. The commercials put forward for example, the tidy mother and the messy boy, quarreling each time. The product tailored for this occasion is a chocolate bar with nuts [12]. Such a tailored text would mean more than any other thing to define such a mother-son relationship. If you could also add a kind of gorilla making, the surrounding even more crabbed you could get more attention. So much that the family detail wouldn't even be noticed there.

Of course, this means **Taking Risks** on the side of the audience. For example the audience should think of what this tailored gorilla item in fact means. Is it a figurative use of the father, assuming that the son had taken after him, as a man, more cluttered, ordinary, and wild? Or does it mean humorously that we are in fact not so different from our cousins, the great apes? All these different ends of thinking would require taking risks when the open texts are disseminated in different ways in different media. Whatever media they appear on they surround the audience through different episodes, different details, reminding and referencing the 'real' text. This **Transmedia** function of the new media collects more responses on behalf of the media and the number of the audiences grows each and every day. This provides more opportunities when the family is questioned because the family members seem to be the different media surrounding the individual all around. You come across with the ice-cream commercials for example, and the father brings the most delicious ice-cream to the family gathering. But as you follow the web site, you see that it was the mother who called him to bring that brand. Yet, in the social media, you see that it was the child whispering the name of the most delicious ice-cream ever into the ears of the grandparents. So, different media makes use of the same idea but in different ways and transmedia impacts all the members of the family in different ways.

Of course, different age groups or social-economic clusters make use of different types of Technology, some lean on the traditional media and older ways of communication, youngsters prefer the new media and new technology. Commercials reaching to the family, also takes care of this issue and mainly the technology is used in the ads as an element of domestication or update for the elder ones in the family. In some cases, the modern grandmothers or fathers get beyond their limits and learn to make use of a better technology to surprise the younger generations. The commercials in this case not only contribute to the development of the technology but also the dissemination of the innovation both in older and newer generation.

In conclusion, the family represented in the commercials is in fact the society itself. The only trouble is that they are only depicted as the happy, ordered, wise and smart ones. Even the naughty ones are accepted as they are. In the commercials, not only the families but also the family systems are portrayed. However, these portrayals do not represent much of the reality in the society. Mostly, tailored occasions are represented aiming to present the family in its best way. These idealized family gatherings or special days supported by the media consumption cannot be the only criteria to develop a family portrayal through the commercials. Family means more intimacy, more feelings and something deeper, but not in a mediatic and pseudo-active way. The reason behind the commercials giving much more importance to the family matters relies on the fact that the family image of the past now is over. It is not only the mothers asking for the shopping list and the fathers are the ones who are paying for it. Rather, all members of a modern family now have almost similar impacts for the purchase decisions and expenses. It means that we'll be coming across more family themes, topics, texts, etc. in commercials.

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